

QUIZ**LAST NAME:** Mohamed**FIRST NAME:** Abdullahi**PROGRAM CODE:** LLM**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401**PERIOD NUMBER:** SIX**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr Gulma

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Commented [GK1]: Note that in US English, personal and academic titles are punctuated. This should be written as **Dr.**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did not use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice10

QUIZ: OVERVIEW LEGAL CITATIONS STYLE

1. In legal writings, citations of certain quotes are not permitted, and their footnotes should appear at the final publications of the written paper. Which is the following being the documents indicated above?

The Law review text.¹

The court documents.

The Law review footnotes.

Legal referendums.

2. The length of citations inserted in a document depends on the volume of information needs of the seeker from the source authority. Name which citation types are never used quotation marks over the written quoted material?

Commented [GK2]: There should not be any space between the period and the superscript. Kindly review all superscripts and made the necessary corrections!

¹ Cooper, et.al., *The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citation*, (Cambridge, Massachusetts: The Harvard Law Association, Gannet House, 2010), 73.

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The 50 and above words citations.²

The less than 50 words quoted citations.

The full sentence citations.

The phrase/clause citations.

3. **In a quotation formatting rule apply for all legal writing standards. In the Bluebook of legal citation style, paragraphing should be observed whenever writing a large citation of over 50 words. Which of these must be demonstrated first?**

Indentations.³

Paragraph structure.

Footnotes of citation place.

Punctuations.

4. **Turabian citation styles are divided into two types. The Author and date style, which inserts its cited material in the text part of the paper in parenthesis. The footnotes and bibliography style of citations is the other type which we are using in this quiz. The two types of citation styles can't be used in the same document. The Author and date style is otherwise called?**

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² [Ibid](#)

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³ [Ibid](#)

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In-text citations.⁴

Footnotes.

Referencing.

Bibliography.

5. Some legal writing words are not allowed to be abbreviated in professional standards of writing legal rules and in education literature. In the Bluebook, some words are found such as: (stay, order, grant, quash, suppress, dismiss, etc.). From the following four words which is among the words unabbreviated word?

Subpoena.⁵

Opinion.

Reporter.

Minutes.

6. When certain words of a quotation are **omitted**, an ellipsis is inserted to indicate missing words. To indicate the missing words an ellipsis is placed in the *beginning* of the sentence or in the *middle* or at the *end*, where the omission happened. When applied in the middle-omitted citations, the rule for inserting ellipsis is?

Commented [GK4]: I suggest you use the shortened citation instead. For example, **Cooper et al., 15** (where 15 is an example of page number). Correct this for other affected citations.

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⁴ Kate, L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers Theses and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ed. Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff. Eighth edition, (Chicago: IL; University of Chicago Press, 2018), 80- 175.

⁵ "Supra." See Cooper et al., 2010.

- Insert the ellipsis where the language is omitted.**⁶
- Insert the ellipsis between the last word being quoted.
- Capitalize the first letter of the quoted language and put Parenthesis.
- Insert the ellipsis before the remainder of the quotation.

7. **Certain punctuation mark is used to separate 3 or 4 words in a series. It is also used after an introductory dependent clause, as well as to indicate independent phrases moved from the end of the sentence. Additionally, they are used between independent clauses joined by coordinating conjunctions (for, and, so, yet, on, but etc.). Which is this type of punctuation explained above?**

- Comma.**⁷
- Period.
- Ellipsis.
- Hyphen.

8. **In Legal documents certain citation words or sentences must be italicized. Which typeface must be written on citations in congressional or committee hearings?**

Commented [GK5]: Correct footnotes 6, 7, and 8 as per the guidance in the comment above!

⁶ See also, Cooper et al., 2010.

⁷ "Ibid". See also: Kate, L. Turabian, 9th ed. 2018.

- Italicized.**⁸
- Underscored.
- Capitalized all.
- Ordinary.

9. **A reporter is a volume of books of records for published written cases given jurisdictions and collected by government institutions like judiciary, Legislature and Administrations, and then stored for references. In this court case cited material which reporter identification volume was used? Bile v. Camey, 397 U.S 189, 220.**

- U. S.**⁹
- S. Ct.
- F.
- F. Supp.

10. **Signals are the introductory words used on documents and other legal literature. Signals show the relationship between the proposition and the source of authority. Which signal abbreviation stands for the words “on behalf of” or “on the relation of”?**

Commented [GK6]: You opted to use US English; all punctuations should be placed inside the inverted comma!

⁸ Accord. to Cooper, “Italicization of titles of books and some other specific citation words”. (Cooper et al., *The Bluebook* 2010.

⁹ “Id”.

- ex-rel.¹⁰
- cf.
- Id./id.
- In-re.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Turabian, Kate L. 9th ed, 2018. *A manual for writers of research papers theses and Dissertations: Chicago style for students and researchers*. Ed. Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff. Chicago: IL; University of Chicago Press.

Tim, Cooper et al. 19th ed. 2010. *The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citation*. Edited by: The Columbia Law review, the Harvard Law review, The University of Pennsylvania Law review, and The Yale Law Journal. Cambridge; Massachusetts: The Harvard law Association, Gennet House.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

¹⁰ See also (cooper et al. The Blue book; A Uniform System of Citation, 2010) 56.

Commented [GK7]: The entries are not as per the formats in the link I shared with you. Kindly refer and review accordingly!